

**MOBIL ILOVALAR ORQALI YOSH BOLALARDA UCHRAYDIGAN NUTQ
BUZILISHLARINI BARTARAF ETISH.**

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Annotatsiya: Ergonomika: Mobil ilovalar yosh bolalar uchun tushunarli bo‘lishi kerak. Ergonomik dizayn bilan mobil ilovalar bolalar uchun qulaylik va foydalanish qulayligini ta‘minlaydi.

Interaktivlik: Nutqni o‘rganish jarayoni o‘zgarishi uchun interaktivlikni talab qiladi. Mobil ilovalarda interaktiv o‘yinlar, musiqa va foydalanuvchini hayratga soladigan boshqa funksiyalar bo‘lishi kerak. Bu bolalarni o‘rganishni yanada qiziqarli qiladi, chunki nutq yuqori.

Ta‘lim: Mobil ilovalar orqali nutq o‘rganish uchun eng foydali bo‘limga aylanishi kerak. O‘quv niqobini o‘z ichiga olgan ta‘lim o‘yinlari yordamida bolalar qiziqarli va oson gapirishni o‘rganishlari mumkin.

Barqarorlik: gapirishni o‘rganish jarayoni odatda ba‘zi amaliyotlar orqali o‘zgaradi. Mobil ilovalardan muntazam foydalanishingizga qarab, farzandingizning nutqni o‘rganish jadvali ustuvor bo‘lishi mumkin.

Xavotirsiz masofa: mobil ilovalar orqali nutqni o‘rganish jarayoni tashvishsiz masofada davom etishini ta‘minlash kerak. Shu bilan birga, talabalar nutqiy vaziyatlarda nutqni o‘rganishni davom ettirishlari mumkin.

Mobil ilovalar orqali nutq buzilishlarini bartaraf etish quyidagi maslahatlarga asoslanishi mumkin.

Kalit so‘zlar: Android studio, Java dasturlash, mobil ilova, platforma, Android qurilma, kompyuter va telefon qurilmalari.

Abstract: Ergonomics: Mobile apps should be easy to understand for young children. With ergonomic design, mobile applications provide comfort and ease of use for children.

Interactivity: The process of learning speech requires interactivity to change. Mobile applications should have interactive games, music and other features that impress the user. This makes it more interesting for children to learn as speech is high.

Education: Speech through mobile applications should be made the most useful section for learning. With the help of educational games that include a learning mask, children can learn to speak in an interesting and easy way.

Consistency: The process of learning to speak normally changes through some practice. Depending on how you use mobile apps on a regular basis, your child's learning schedule for speaking can become a priority.

Worry-free distance: It is necessary to ensure that the process of learning speech through mobile applications can be continued at a worry-free distance. At the same time, students can continue to study speaking in speaking situations.

Eliminating speech disorders through mobile applications can be based on the following tips:

Keywords: *Android studio, Java programming, mobile application, platform, Android device, computer and phone settings.*

Абстрактный: *Эргономика. Мобильные приложения должны быть понятны маленьким детям. Благодаря эргономичному дизайну мобильные приложения обеспечивают комфорт и простоту использования для детей.*

Интерактивность. Процесс обучения речи требует изменения интерактивности. Мобильные приложения должны иметь интерактивные игры, музыку и другие функции, которые впечатляют пользователя. Это делает обучение детей более интересным, поскольку речь становится высокой.

Образование: Речь через мобильные приложения следует сделать максимально полезным разделом для обучения. С помощью развивающих игр, в состав которых входит обучающая маска, дети могут научиться говорить интересно и легко.

Последовательность: Процесс обучения нормальной речи меняется с помощью некоторой практики. В зависимости от того, как вы регулярно используете мобильные приложения, график обучения речи вашего ребенка может стать приоритетом.

Дистанция без беспокойства: необходимо обеспечить, чтобы процесс обучения речи с помощью мобильных приложений можно было продолжать на безопасном расстоянии. При этом студенты могут продолжать учиться говорению в речевых ситуациях.

Устранить речевые нарушения посредством мобильных приложений можно на основе следующих советов:

Ключевые слова: *Android-студия, Java-программирование, мобильное приложение, платформа, Android-устройство, настройки компьютера и телефона*

Asosiy qism.

Bugungi kuning eng dolzarb muommalaridan biri bu yosh avlodning to‘g‘ri ta‘lim tarbiya ,aqliy va sog‘lom, nutqiy rivojlanishi juda katta ahamiyatga egadur muxtaram prezidintimiz Sh.Mirziyoyev bejizga “Yuqori sinflarda bolalar shaxs

bo‘lib, jamoa bo‘lib shakllanadi. Ayni o‘sha paytda ularni o‘zlari o‘rgangan muhitdan ajratib qo‘ymaslik kerak. Bu yoshlarning ruhiyatiga, davomatiga, oxir-oqibatda ta‘lim-tarbiyasiga salbiy ta‘sir qilishi mumkin. Shu bois ta‘lim jarayonining usluksizligini ta‘minlash, o‘quv dasturlarini takomillashtirish zarur”. aytmagan shu sababli biz maktab yoshdagi bolalarning nutqiy rivojlanishida mobil ilovalar ishlab chiqishga harakat qildik. Bu mobil ilova orqali nutqni o‘rganish jarayonida amaliyotlarni o‘rganishni ta‘dbiq etish, ovozlantirish ko‘nikmalari, atrofda tilni to‘g‘ri ishlatishni biriktirish va gapirish o‘yinlarini o‘ynash yordamida nutqni rivojlanishini amalga oshirish mumkin.

Nutq turlari. Kishilar tildan fikr bayon qilish quroli sifatida foydalanadilar. Ular o‘z fikrlarini ovoz bilan eshittirib bayon qilishdan oldin u haqda o‘ylab oladilar. Bu ichki nutq hisoblanadi. Ichki nutq eshittirilmagan va yozilmagan “o‘ylangan” (fikrlangan) nutqdir. Tashqi nutq tovushlar yordamida eshittirilib yoki grafik belgilar bilan yozilib, boshqalarga qaratilgan nutqdir. Ichki nutq materialni tushunish va yodda saqlashga yordam beradi. Fikrni ifodalash usuliga ko‘ra nutq og‘zaki va yozma bo‘ladi. Og‘zaki nutq ko‘pincha dialog tarzida, yozma nutq esa monolog tarzida bo‘ladi. O‘quvchilar nutqiga qo‘yilgan talablar. O‘quvchilar nutqini o‘stirishda aniq belgilangan bir qator talablarga rioya qilinadi.

1. O‘quvchilar nutqi mazmundor bo‘lsin.
2. Nutqda mantiqiylik bo‘lsin.
3. Nutq aniq bo‘lsin.
4. Nutq til vositalariga boy bo‘lsin.
5. Nutq tushunarli bo‘lsin.
6. Nutq ifodali bo‘lsin.
7. Nutq to‘g‘ri bo‘lsin

Mobil ilovalar orqali nutqni o'rganish jarayonida kamera va mikrofonni foydalanish orqali ham hal qilish mumkin. Ushbu vositalarni qo'llash bilan, bolalar o'qish, nutqni rivojlantirish jarayonlari haqida ko'plab materiallar yaratish va ularda o'zaro axborot almashinuvi oson.

Mobil ilovalar orqali nutq buzilishlarini bartaraf etish quyidagi rasmda ko'rsatilgan ovaz chastatalari orqali to'g'rilanadi

Ergonomik dizayn, interaktivlik va ta'lim imkoniyatlari orqali yosh bolalar uchun qulay nutq o'rganish jarayonini ta'minlash. Masalan Bir yarim - ikki yoshda bola sodda gaplarni tuza oladi. Sababi bu davrda uning nutqida fe'llar paydo bo'la boshlaydi. Ikki yoshgacha bola ishlata oladigan so'zlar miqdori 60-80 taga etishi kerak. Ana shundan keyin **u x, y** tovushlarini ayta boshlaydi. Bu paytda u hali **r, sh, j, l, ch** kabi ayrim tovushlarni aytmashligi mumkin va bu me'yor sanaladi ammo bazi bir maktab o'quvchilari maktabda ham bu hariflarning talafuzini aytishga qiynaladi bu dasturda o'quvchiga bu hariflardan tashkil topgan so'zlar beriladi o'quvchi bu so'zlarni talafuz qilib recorder orqali yuboradi dastur sizga shu so'zning qancha miqdorda to'g'ri aytilganini ko'rsatib beradi bolalar bu dasturdan uzluksiz ravishda ko'p foydalansa nutqlari tengqurlariga nisbatan ancha rivojlanadi.

Xulosa.

Mobil ilovani yaratishdan maqsad, bolalarni maktabgacha ta’lim bilan qamrab olishni kengaytirish, maktabgacha ta’lim tashkilotlariga bormaydigan bolalarga ta’lim xizmatlari ko’rsatishdan iborat. Mobil ilovalar bilan amaliyotlarni o’rganish, qo’llab-quvvatlash va tajriba mashg’alalari yordamida nutqni o’rganishning paydo bo’lishini ta’minlash. Kamera va mikrofonni foydalanish orqali bolalarni nutqni o’rganishga oilaviy axborot almashishga qo’llash yaratish. Bola uch yoshdan to’rt yoshgacha — 1000 ta, to’rt yoshdan besh yoshgacha — 2000 ta, besh yoshdan oshganda esa 3000 ga yaqin so’zni bilsa uning nutqiy rivojlanishi me’yor darajasida bo’ladi. Besh yoshli bolada barcha tovushlar talaffuzi shakllangan bo’lib, u rasm asosida biror hikoyani qayta gapirib bera oladi.

Bu maslahatlar bilan, mobil ilovalar orqali maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda uchraydigan nutq buzilishlarini bartaraf etish mumkin. Bu usul va vositalar bilan, bolalar nutqni o’rganish jarayonini qiziqishli, qulay va samarali qilish imkonini topishlari mumkin.

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